

CEC News

100 YEARS
विकसित भारत
अभियान
1947 TO 2047

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प्रिय पाठकों,

शैक्षिक संचार संकाय (सीईसी) अपनी स्थापना के बाद से ही शिक्षार्थियों को उच्चतम क्षमता वाले डिजिटल शिक्षण संसाधन प्रदान करने की दिशा में ठोस योजना के साथ प्रयासरत है। हम पूरे देशभर में कार्यशालाएं और सेमिनार आयोजन के माध्यम से शिक्षकों को प्रशिक्षित और विकसित करने की अपनी सतत प्रतिबद्धता के साथ कार्य कर रहे हैं। यह सुनिश्चित करता है कि सीईसी से संबद्ध प्रत्येक विशेषज्ञ अपने विषय और शैक्षिक प्रगति के बारे में विशेषज्ञता के साथ ही डिजिटल प्रौद्योगिकियों की अच्छी समझ रखते हैं। शिक्षार्थियों के लाभ के लिए सीईसी से संबद्ध 21 शैक्षिक मल्टीमीडिया अनुसंधान केंद्र (ईएमआरसी) उत्कृष्ट स्तर की शैक्षणिक सामग्री बनाने के लिए सजगता से प्रयासरत हैं, जिसे यूट्यूब चैनल, डीटीएच चैनल, ई-कोर्सवेयर और स्वयं मूक्स कोर्स (एमओओसी) सहित विभिन्न प्लेटफॉर्म के माध्यम से प्राप्त किया जा सकता है।

देश की डिजिटल शैक्षिक प्रगति के तरफ बढ़ते कदमों में सीईसी की भूमिका महत्वपूर्ण रही है। हम स्वयं और स्वयंप्रभा प्लेटफॉर्म के माध्यम से विभिन्न विषयों के स्नातक (यूजी) और स्नातकोत्तर (पीजी) छात्रों के लिए मूक्स पाठ्यक्रम प्रदान कर रहे हैं। साथ ही देशभर के विश्वविद्यालयों के सक्षम संकाय सदस्यों द्वारा सीधा प्रसारित (लाइव) और रिकॉर्डेड व्याख्यान श्रृंखला को उच्च शिक्षा के 24*7 डिजिटल चैनल 'व्यास' पर प्रसारण कर रहे हैं, जिससे शिक्षार्थियों को कहीं भी और कभी भी सीखने की सुविधा प्रदान की जा रही है। पूरे देश के शिक्षार्थियों की भाषायी विविधता को ध्यान में रखते हुए हम कई पाठ्यक्रमों को विभिन्न क्षेत्रीय भाषाओं में अनुवादित कर प्रस्तुत कर रहे हैं। हम विभिन्न भौगोलिक परिस्थितियों वाले छात्रों और शिक्षार्थियों की जरूरतों को ध्यान में रखकर उन्हें एक समावेशी शैक्षणिक वातावरण प्रदान करने को प्रयासरत हैं।

सीईसी डिजिटल शिक्षा के उद्देश्य को प्रगति के रास्ते पर आगे बढ़ाते हुए दूर-दराज के शिक्षार्थियों को गुणवत्तापूर्ण डिजिटल शैक्षणिक सामग्री पहुंचाने का कार्य जारी रखेगा।

जय हिन्द!

जगत भूषण नड्डा
निदेशक - सी.ई.सी.

Dear Readers,

Since its founding, CEC has made a concerted effort to offer students the highest calibre digital learning resources. We organise workshops and seminars throughout the nation as part of our diligent commitment to train and develop teachers. This guarantees that every expert working with CEC is knowledgeable about academic advancements across subjects and is well-versed in digital technologies. CEC's 21 Educational Multimedia Research Centres are actively working to create top-notch educational content that can be accessed through various platforms, including YouTube, DTH Channels, e-courseware, and MOOCs, for the benefit of our students.

CEC's role in digital educational advancements in the country has been pivotal. We offer UG and PG Massive Open Online Courses across diverse disciplines through SWAYAM and SWAYAM Prabha. Vyas, our 24X7 DTH Channel for Higher Education streams both, live and recorded lectures facilitated by competent faculty members from universities across India allowing learners to learn anywhere and anytime. Keeping in mind, the diversity of learners from across India, our courses have been translated into several regional languages. We strive to provide an inclusive learning environment regardless of our learners' geographic location bridging the gap between students and learners.

CEC shall continue to provide quality digital educational content to the remotest learners furthering the cause of Digital Education.

Jai Hind!!

Jagat Bhushan Nadda
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DIGITAL EDUCATION: EMPOWERING HIGHER EDUCATION THROUGH BLENDED LEARNING

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In an era defined by rapid technological advancement and evolving educational paradigms, the landscape of higher education is undergoing a profound transformation. Digital education, characterized by the integration of technology into pedagogical approaches, has emerged as a cornerstone in reshaping the way students learn and educators teach. This synergistic approach not only enhances accessibility and flexibility but also enriches the learning experience by catering to diverse learning styles and fostering collaboration and engagement. As we delve into the realm of digital education and explore its potential to empower higher education, it becomes evident that the convergence of technology and pedagogy holds immense promise in equipping learners with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

Blended learning, the integration of online and in-person instruction, has emerged as a powerful tool for educators seeking to adapt to the demands of the digital age while preserving the value of face-to-face interaction.

Benefits of Blended Learning in Higher Education:

Blended learning in higher education offers a plethora of benefits that enhance the overall learning experience and outcomes for students. Here are some key advantages:

Fig 2: Benefits of Blended Learning

Fig 1: Blended Learning (Source: <https://www.nshmc.com/a-beautiful-rainbow-of-blended-learning/>)

Flexibility and Accessibility: Blended learning provides students with the flexibility to access course materials and engage in learning activities at their own pace and convenience. This flexibility is especially beneficial for non-traditional students,

working professionals, and those with diverse learning needs or physical disabilities, allowing them to pursue higher education without geographical or time constraints.

Personalized Learning Experience: By integrating online resources, multimedia content, and interactive activities, blended learning caters to individual learning styles and preferences. Students can choose the mode of learning that best suits them, whether it's watching video lectures, participating in online discussions, or engaging in hands-on activities.

Enhanced Engagement and Collaboration: Blended learning environments promote active learning through collaborative activities, discussions, and group projects both online and in the classroom. Through online forums, social media platforms, and virtual collaboration tools, students can interact with peers and instructors, share ideas, and collaborate on projects regardless of physical location.

Real-world Application and Skill Development: Blended learning often incorporates real-world scenarios, case studies, and interactive simulations that bridge the gap between theory and practice. Students have the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts to practical situations, develop problem-solving skills, and gain hands-on experience using digital tools and technologies relevant to their field of study.

Data-Driven Insights and Personalized Feedback: Digital learning platforms and tools often collect data on student progress, engagement, and performance, allowing instructors to track individual student's progress in real-time. This data-driven approach enables instructors to provide timely feedback, identify areas of strength and weakness, and tailor instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of students.

Cost and Resource Efficiency: Blended learning can lead to cost savings for both students and institutions by reducing the need for physical infrastructure, such as classrooms and textbooks, and optimizing the use of educational resources. By leveraging digital technologies, institutions can deliver high-quality educational content to a larger audience at a lower cost, making higher education more accessible and affordable.

Challenges of Blended Learning in Higher Education

Fig 3: Challenges of Blended Learning

Digital Divide: Despite the increasing accessibility of technology, disparities in access to digital resources and internet connectivity persist among student populations. The digital divide can hinder the effectiveness of blended learning initiatives, particularly for students from low-income backgrounds or rural areas who may lack access to reliable internet connections or necessary devices.

Technical Challenges and Support Needs: Technical issues such as software compatibility issues, network disruptions, and system glitches can disrupt the learning experience and impede student engagement. Additionally, faculty and staff may require ongoing training and support to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices.

Pedagogical Integration: Successful implementation of blended learning requires careful alignment between pedagogical goals, instructional design, and technological tools. Some educators may struggle to effectively integrate digital resources into their teaching practices or may encounter resistance to change from students accustomed to traditional classroom instruction.

Maintaining Engagement and Motivation: While blended learning offers opportunities for interactive and personalized learning experiences, maintaining student engagement and motivation can be challenging, especially in online components where students may feel isolated or disengaged. Designing engaging and interactive online activities, fostering a sense of community through virtual discussions and collaborative projects, and providing timely feedback are essential strategies for mitigating this limitation.

Assessment and Academic Integrity: Assessing student learning in blended learning environments poses unique challenges, particularly in ensuring academic integrity and preventing cheating in online assessments. Designing authentic and meaningful assessments that accurately measure student learning outcomes while deterring academic dishonesty requires careful consideration and implementation of assessment strategies, such as proctored exams, alternative assessments, and plagiarism detection tools.

Future Prospects of Blended Learning in Higher Education

Fig 4: Future Prospects of Blended Learning

Innovation and Adaptability: Blended learning offers a flexible and adaptable approach to teaching and learning that can evolve to meet the changing needs and preferences of students and educators. As technology continues to advance, the potential for innovation in blended learning environments is virtually limitless, with opportunities to integrate emerging technologies to enhance learning outcomes and create immersive learning experiences.

Customization and Personalization: Blended learning enables personalized learning pathways tailored to individual student needs, preferences, and learning styles. By leveraging data analytics and adaptive learning platforms, educators can customize instruction, provide targeted interventions, and support student success through personalized feedback, remediation, and enrichment activities.

Global Collaboration and Connectivity: Blended learning transcends geographical boundaries, allowing students and educators to connect and collaborate with peers and experts from around the world. Virtual classrooms, online forums, and collaborative projects facilitate cross-cultural exchange, interdisciplinary collaboration, and global networking opportu-

nities, enriching the learning experience and preparing students for success in a globally interconnected society.

Lifelong Learning and Professional Development: Blended learning offers opportunities for educators to engage in continuous professional development, explore innovative teaching strategies, and enhance their pedagogical practices through online courses, webinars, and virtual communities of practice.

Accessibility and Inclusivity: Blended learning has the potential to enhance accessibility and inclusivity in higher education by accommodating diverse learner needs and preferences. Through the use of assistive technologies, captioned videos, and accessible course materials, blended learning environments can remove barriers to learning for students with disabilities and create more inclusive learning environments that celebrate diversity and promote equity.

In conclusion, Blended Learning represents a pivotal shift in the landscape of educational paradigms, signalling a transformative journey towards enhanced learning experiences. Blended learning, with its fusion of traditional classroom methods and digital technology, emerges as a potent tool in the arsenal of higher education institutions, offering unparalleled flexibility, accessibility, and personalized learning pathways.

Moreover, the advent of digital technologies has democratized access to education, levelling the playing field for learners worldwide. Whether through virtual classrooms, collaborative online platforms, or mobile learning applications, students now have the opportunity to engage with educational content anytime, anywhere, empowering them to take ownership of their learning journey. By nurturing digital literacy skills and fostering a culture of continuous learning, higher education institutions can equip individuals with the tools and competencies needed to thrive in the digital age. However, it is crucial to acknowledge the challenges and considerations associated with implementing blended learning initiatives, including technological infrastructure, faculty training, and ensuring equitable access for all learners. Addressing these obstacles requires a concerted effort from stakeholders across academia, industry, and government to create an enabling environment conducive to innovation and collaboration. ★

Disclaimer: Views expressed in the article are personal.

FROM CHALKBOARDS TO SCREENS: TRANSFORMING TEACHER EDUCATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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T

he digital age has revolutionized education, shifting from traditional methods to interactive screens. To ensure that teachers are prepared for this new era of learning, this transformation necessitates a parallel evolution in teacher education programs. This article examines the ways that innovative tools, ethical considerations, adaptive teaching strategies, historical evolution, and essential competencies are reshaping teacher education.

Historical Perspectives: Tracing the Evolution of Educational Technology

Historical analysis reveals key periods in the development of educational technology. While audio-visual aids of the 20th century revolutionized teaching, the printing press democratized knowledge. The introduction of computers in the late 20th century completely changed education. Access to educational resources is now unmatched thanks to the

internet and mobile devices. This historical viewpoint emphasizes the importance of technology in education and the necessity for educators to change. Teachers can use contemporary tools to improve student learning experiences by having a thorough understanding of this evolution.

Digital Literacy for Educators: Key Competencies in the Modern Classroom

In the contemporary classroom, digital literacy is a fundamental competency for teachers, encompassing technological competence, information literacy, cybersecurity awareness, digital communication skills, efficient online pedagogy, and keeping up with educational technology. It enables educators to use technology to enhance teaching and learning, promote digital citizenship, and ensure inclusive and accessible digital resources. Developing these competencies allows teachers to become more effective educators and equip their students with essential skills for the digital age, making digital literacy a

cornerstone of transformative teacher education in the transition from chalkboards to screens.

Adaptive Teaching Strategies: Personalizing Learning in Digital Environments

Thanks to technology-driven adaptive teaching strategies, personalized learning experiences are at their peak in the digital age. These techniques give teachers the ability to adapt their lessons to the particular needs, interests, and skills of each student. This revolutionary method is drastically altering teacher preparation. The first step is to comprehend the various learner profiles and then use data to tailor instruction. Adaptive platforms provide the right amount of challenge by dynamically adjusting the pace and content. Growth mindsets are promoted by varied resources and tailored feedback. Targeted interventions are seamlessly integrated for students with different needs. This approach fosters critical thinking, supports independent learning, and connects what is learned in the classroom to practical applications. Teachers create inclusive and dynamic learning environments by implementing adaptive teaching strategies, thereby preparing students for a future characterized by flexibility and lifelong learning.

The Ethical Dimensions: Navigating Privacy and Equity in Digital Education

The moral dimensions of privacy and equity have become crucial factors in teacher education as the field embraces the digital era. It is now critical to protect student data and maintain privacy online. Teachers need to understand the ramifications of sharing student data with third-party platforms and negotiate complicated environments while abiding by data protection laws. Furthermore, advancing fairness in education requires ensuring equal access to technology. Preemptively recognizing and resolving discrepancies in device accessibility and dependable internet connectivity are necessary for this. Educators have a crucial duty to teach students digital citizenship, which includes appropriate online conduct and respect for one's privacy. Teachers contribute to a digital learning environment that supports the values of fairness, inclusivity, and responsible behavior by addressing these ethical aspects. A key component of transformative teacher preparation in the digital age is this thoughtful approach to digital education.

Innovative Tools and Platforms: Enhancing Instructional Effectiveness

The integration of innovative tools and platforms in education has revolutionized the teaching and learning process. These technologies include interactive whiteboards, smart displays, Learning Management Systems (LMS), virtual reality and AR, gamification, video conferencing, and AI and machine learning. These tools enhance engagement and collaboration, provide a centralized repository for course materials, assessments, and communication, and offer immersive virtual environments. Gamification and educational games make learning more engaging and memorable. Video conferencing and collaborative online platforms enable real-time interaction, transcending geographical constraints. AI and machine learning offer individualized learning experiences by modifying the content according to each learner's progress. This integration not only increases the efficacy of instruction but also gives students the tools they need to live in a world that is increasingly reliant on technology.

Professional Development in a Digital World: Empowering Educators

Digital professional development has become a vital pillar in enabling teachers in the quickly changing educational landscape. Teachers need to be lifelong learners in order to properly use digital tools and approaches as technology continues to change the context of the classroom. This covers a wide range of offerings, including webinars, workshops, and online courses, all with the goal of improving teaching effectiveness in the digital age. By providing educators with the information and abilities needed to success-

fully negotiate the challenges of digital education, professional development programs encourage flexibility and creativity. Incorporating cutting-edge tools and platforms is another thing they help with, which eventually improves students' educational experience. In an increasingly technology-driven world, educators who embrace digital professional development not only strengthen their own skills but also set the groundwork for the success of the coming generation. The way that professional development practices are evolving highlights how important it is to improving educational outcomes in the digital age.

Transformative Dimensions of Digital Education

In the digital era, assessing learning in virtual spaces requires a paradigm shift in evaluation methods. Tech-driven approaches use diverse assessment tools, including interactive quizzes and personalized real-time analytics. Maintaining assessment integrity is challenging, leading to innovations like remote proctoring. Proficiency with these tools is crucial for effective virtual teaching and accurate student evaluation.

This change is a turning point in knowledge acquisition and sharing, going beyond technology to transform teaching methods. It replaces passive learning

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with dynamic, personalized approaches, utilizing virtual and multimedia experiences to enhance engagement. This shift encourages global connectivity and cooperation, prompting a reevaluation of teaching roles, ultimately redefining education in an interconnected, information-rich world, equipping students with essential 21st-century skills.

Modern education necessitates empowering educators to be proficient with virtual reality, interactive technology, and learning systems. Teachers adapt their approaches for the online environment using online forums and multimedia resources, ensuring a secure learning environment through cybersecurity and digital literacy. Realizing the full potential of the digital classroom requires customized training and professional development, producing technologically literate students prepared for a tech-fluent future.

Balancing Tradition with Technology: Navigating Pedagogical Changes

In order to navigate pedagogical shifts, striking a balance between tradition and technology in the classroom is essential. While the fundamentals of good teaching remain unchanged, technology has fundamentally altered the nature of education. It's crucial to thoughtfully integrate digital tools to support established teaching methodologies rather than replacing them. Educators must discern when to use technology to enhance understanding and participation. Striking this delicate balance enables the enhancement of learning experiences through technology while upholding crucial aspects of traditional education, such as critical thinking and interpersonal interaction. By adeptly managing these pedagogical shifts, teachers create an environment where students are prepared for success in the digital age, merging cutting-edge technology with time-tested educational principles.

आईयूएसी ने राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस मनाया

अंतर विश्वविद्यालय त्वरक केंद्र (आईयूएसी), नई दिल्ली ने 10 और 11 मई, 2024 को राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस मनाया। राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस पोखरण (राजस्थान) में देश के सफल ऐतिहासिक परमाणु परीक्षणों को स्मरण करने के अवसर पर हर वर्ष 11 मई को मनाया जाता है। इस दिवस को विज्ञान, प्रौद्योगिकी और नवाचार के क्षेत्र में देश की उतरोत्तर प्रगति को स्मरण करने के लिए कई वर्षों से मनाया जा रहा है। ऐतिहासिक अवसर को इस वर्ष मनाने की विषय-वस्तु 'विकसित भारत @ 2047 हेतु विदेशी तकनीक' था।

सीईसी के निदेशक प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा इस अवसर पर मुख्य अतिथि के रूप में शामिल हुए। अपने भाषण में प्रो. नड्डा ने कहा कि तकनीक केवल उपकरणों के बारे में नहीं बल्कि यह दुनिया को एक बेहतर स्थान बनाने से संबद्ध है। राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस पर आईयूएसी की ओर से शिक्षार्थियों के लिए विशेष व्याख्यान का आयोजन किया गया। व्याख्यान में सम्मिलित दिल्ली के विभिन्न स्कूलों के युवा प्रतिभाओं से बातचीत में प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा ने उन्हें अपने सपनों को आगे बढ़ाने और उज्ज्वल भविष्य की दिशा में काम करने के लिए प्रेरित किया। छात्रों ने आईयूएसी परिसर में नवाचार से जुड़े मॉडल आदि पर एक प्रदर्शनी भी लगाई।

राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस के अवसर पर रक्षा अनुसंधान एवं विकास संगठन (डीआरडीओ), वैज्ञानिक तथा औद्योगिक अनुसंधान परिषद (सीएसआईआर) आदि संस्थानों के प्रख्यात वैज्ञानिक, अधिकारियों के साथ ही शैक्षिक संचार संकाय (सीईसी) के तकनीकी क्षेत्र से संबद्ध कर्मचारी सम्मिलित हुए।

Prof. J.B.Nadda, Director, CEC lights the lamp at National Technology Day celebrations, IUAC, New Delhi
प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा, निदेशक- सीईसी, आईयूएसी (नई दिल्ली) में आयोजित राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस समारोह में दीप प्रज्वलित करते हुए।

National Technology Day Celebrations @IUAC

The Inter-University Accelerator Centre, New Delhi, celebrated National Technology Day on the 10th and 11th of May, 2024. The National Technology Day is celebrated every year on the 11th of May to commemorate India's historic nuclear tests carried out in Pokhran, Rajasthan. It is also a day celebrating India's advancement in science, technology and innovation over the years. This year the theme of the celebration was Vikshit Bharat 2047 Hetu Videshi Takniki.

Prof. J.B. Nadda, Director, CEC, was invited to the event as Chief Guest, during his speech he said, "Technology isn't just about gadgets: it's about making the world a better place." On the occasion, special lectures were organised by the institute for students. Prof. J.B. Nadda interacted with young minds from various schools of Delhi, motivating them to pursue their dreams and work towards a brighter future. The students also put up an exhibition displaying innovative models and projects on campus.

Eminent scientists and staff members from institutions like DRDO, CSIR etc. and CEC's technical staff attended the event.

Prof. J.B. Nadda, Director, CEC, inaugurates National Technology Day celebrations at IUAC, New Delhi

राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी दिवस पर आईयूएसी (नई दिल्ली) में आयोजित समारोह का उद्घाटन करते हुए प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा, निदेशक- सीईसी।

Prof. J.B. Nadda, Director, CEC, interacts with students

कार्यक्रम में छात्रों से वार्तालाप करते हुए प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा, निदेशक- सीईसी।

ईएमआरसी कालीकट में दो दिवसीय कार्यशाला का आयोजन

शैक्षिक मल्टीमीडिया अनुसंधान केंद्र (ईएमआरसी) कालीकट में स्वयंप्रभा-2.0 से जुड़े विषय पर 16 और 17 मई, 2024 को दो दिवसीय कार्यशाला का आयोजन किया गया। कार्यशाला का उद्घाटन शैक्षिक संचार संकाय (सीईसी) के निदेशक प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा ने किया। इस कार्यक्रम में कालीकट विश्वविद्यालय के कुलपति प्रो. एम. के. जयरज सम्मानित अतिथि के रूप में सम्मिलित हुए।

उद्घाटन-सत्र के अपने भाषण में सीईसी के निदेशक प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा ने देशभर में शिक्षार्थियों की आवश्यकताओं को पूरा करने के लिए स्वयंप्रभा डीटीएच चैनलों की विस्तार क्षमता आदि का पता लगाने की आवश्यकता पर जोर दिया। दो दिवसीय कार्यशाला को सफल बनाने के लिए स्वयंप्रभा डीटीएच चैनल से संबद्ध ईएमआरसी के अधिकारियों, कर्मचारियों ने सक्रिय रूप से भागीदारी निभाई। दो दिवसीय कार्यक्रम का सुचारु संचालन सुनिश्चित करने आदि में सीईसी की ओर से प्रो. रजनीश श्रीवास्तव- अपर निदेशक, सुश्री दिशा अवतार, डॉ. अस्मिता बख्शी ने सहभागिता की।

Prof. M.K. Jayaraj, Vice-Chancellor, University of Calicut (R), welcomes Prof. J.B. Nadda, Director, CEC. कार्यक्रम में प्रो. जे. बी. नड्डा, निदेशक- सीईसी का स्वागत करते हुए कालीकट विश्वविद्यालय के कुलपति प्रो. एम. के. जयरज (दाएं)।

2-Day Workshop organised at EMRC Calicut

A 2-day workshop on SWAYAM Prabha 2.0 was organised at EMRC Calicut, on the 16th and 17th of May, 2024. The workshop was inaugurated by Prof. J. B. Nadda, Director, CEC. Prof. M. K. Jayaraj, Vice-Chancellor, University of Calicut was the guest of Honor for the event.

In the inaugural address, Prof. J.B.Nadda, Director, CEC, emphasised the need to explore the potential of SWAYAM Prabha DTH channels to satisfy the country's educational needs. EMRC staff members, dealing with DTH channels actively participated in the workshop, making it a success. CEC staff members, Dr Rajnish Srivastav, Additional Director, CEC, Ms Disha Avtar and Mrs. Asmita Bakshi attended the workshop and ensured its smooth functioning.

EMRC Directors and staff members participate in the 2-day workshop
दो दिवसीय कार्यशाला में सम्मिलित मीडिया केंद्रों के निदेशक, कर्मचारियों और अन्य के साथ।

ईएमआरसी मैसूर ने एनसीईआरटी राष्ट्रीय ई-कंटेंट प्रतियोगिता में जीते 2 शीर्ष पुरस्कार

ईएमआरसी मैसूर के तकनीशियन श्री के. गोपीनाथ ने नॉर्थ ईस्ट रीजनल इंस्टीट्यूट ऑफ एजुकेशन- शिलांग, मेघालय में आयोजित अखिल भारतीय बाल शिक्षा ई-कंटेंट प्रतियोगिता (एआईसीईसीसी 2023-24) के सेकेंडरी श्रेणी में प्रतिष्ठित सर्वश्रेष्ठ वीडियो का पुरस्कार हासिल किया। सीआईईईटी-एनसीईआरटी, नई दिल्ली द्वारा आयोजित समारोह में मेघालय के शिक्षा मंत्री श्री रक्कम ए. संगमा ने विजेताओं को पुरस्कार प्रदान किए। नॉर्थ ईस्ट रीजनल इंस्टीट्यूट ऑफ एजुकेशन- शिलांग में आयोजित समारोह में विजेताओं को पुरस्कार प्रदान किए। पुरस्कृत ई-कंटेंट 'द इनोवेटिव फॉर्मर' को मिले सम्मान के दौरान अतिथियों में प्रो. सकलेजा, निदेशक- एनसीईआरटी और प्रो. अमरेन्द्र पी. बहेराम, संयुक्त निदेशक-सीआईईईटी की मौजूदगी भी रही। श्री के. गोपीनाथ ने इसके अलावा वृत्तचित्र 'तुलसी- मदर ऑफ फोरेस्ट' में सर्वश्रेष्ठ संगीत संयोजन का पुरस्कार भी हासिल किया। अखिल भारतीय बाल शिक्षा ई-कंटेंट प्रतियोगिता महोत्सव के लिए आयोजकों को देशभर से कुल 437 प्रतिभागियों की प्रविष्टियां प्राप्त हुई थीं।

EMRC Mysore Bags 2 Top Awards in NCERT's National E-content Contest

Mr K. Gopinath, Technician, EMRC Mysore, was bestowed with the prestigious Best Video Award in the Secondary Level category during the All India Children's Educational E-content Competition (AICECC-2023-24) hosted at the North East Regional Institute of Education (NERIE) in Shillong, Meghalaya. The award was presented by Shri. Rakkma Sangma, Minister of Education, Meghalaya, in the event organised by CIET-NCERT, New Delhi. The winning e-content, titled "The Innovative Farmer", garnered recognition among esteemed attendees, including Prof. Sakleja, Director of NCERT, and Prof. Amarendra P. Baheram, Joint Director CIET. Furthermore, Mr. K. Gopinath bagged another award for Best Music Design with the documentary "Tulasi - Mother of Forest". Notably, the festival attracted a remarkable total of 437 entries from participants across the country.

एमओई अधिकारियों ने बताए 'अपार', 'एबीसी' से जुड़े लाभ

उस्मानिया विश्वविद्यालय के निदेशक श्री पी. रघुपति के बतौर प्रतिनिधि निर्माण एवं तकनीकी टीम के कर्मचारियों ने शिक्षा मंत्रालय (भारत सरकार) के साथ दिनांक 02 मई 2024 को ऑनलाइन बैठक में हिस्सा लिया। इस बैठक में मंत्रालय के अधिकारियों ने देशभर के सभी शिक्षार्थियों को लाभान्वित करने वाली नवीनतम पहल ऑटोमेटेड परमानेंट एकेडमिक एकाउंट रजिस्ट्री (अपार) एवं एकेडमिक बैंक ऑफ क्रेडिट्स (एबीसी) के कार्यान्वयन की जरूरत और महत्व के बारे में विस्तार से समझाया। केंद्र की इस पहल 'अपार' के तहत देश के हर शिक्षार्थी की स्कूल से लेकर उच्च शिक्षा हासिल करने तक एक विशिष्ट पहचान पंजीकरण संख्या होगी। 'एबीसी' कार्यान्वयन में शिक्षा हासिल करने के दौरान हर शिक्षार्थी के अर्जित क्रेडिट्स की जानकारी वर्चुअल/ डिजिटल रूप में संग्रहित करने का प्रावधान मिलेगा। इस ऑनलाइन बैठक में ईएमआरसी उस्मानिया विश्वविद्यालय के प्रतिनिधियों द्वारा पूछे गए सभी सवालों का जबाब मंत्रालय के अधिकारियों ने विस्तारपूर्वक समझाकर दिया। इस दौरान उन्होंने ईएमआरसी के प्रतिभागियों से अपने विश्वविद्यालय में 'अपार' और 'एबीसी' के कार्यान्वयन में अहम भूमिका निभाने को भी कहा।

MoE throws light on APAAR and ABC, Explains Benefits

On behalf of Osmania University, Shri P. Raghupathi, Director, along with the production & technical staff of the Center attended an online meeting with the Ministry of Education, Govt. of India on 02.05.2024. The officials of the Ministry explained the need and importance of implementing the Automated Permanent Academic Account Registry (APAAR) and Academic Bank of Credits (ABC), the latest initiatives of the Government of India for the benefit of all the students in the country. APAAR is a unique identification number assigned to each student in India, from pre-primary to higher education. ABC is a virtual/digital storehouse that contains information on the credits earned by individual students throughout their learning journey. The officials of the Ministry were kind enough to answer all the queries raised by the EMRC. They asked the EMRC to lead in implementing APAAR and ABC in the University.

Subject Expert
SHALLU SACHDEVA

Affiliation

Professor, Chemistry,
Acharya Narendra Dev
College, University of Delhi

Title

**ENERGY IN THE
ENVIRONMENT-I**

Scan for lecture

About the Expert

Professor Shallu Sachdeva has graduated in Chemistry (Hons) from Miranda House, University of Delhi and M.Sc. (gold medallist) and Ph.D. in Chemistry from the Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi. She teaches Chemistry, at Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi. She has many research papers in various reputed national and international journals and has contributed chapters in national and international books. She is also a member of many learned bodies. She has delivered several lectures at various national and international conferences and summits. She has also delivered lectures and invited speakers to educational summits by ELETS and organised multiple workshops and conferences. She is a recipient of the Global Academic Research Excellence Award of Best Faculty in Chemical Sciences-MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow and Proud Indian Iconic Reader and Researcher Award 2023- Ratna Prasad Multidisciplinary Research and Educational Society. Apart from this, she has also been a subject matter expert at NCERT.

Excerpt from the Lecture

Various sources of energy are available in the environment like sun, wind and fossils which are being used by humans to carry out various activities. The main source of energy is the Sun. The consumption of energy by a nation depends upon its population and hence economic growth. Solar energy is a form of renewable energy available in abundance and can be used for the production of electricity, apart from a number of other applications. Wind and water are also energy sources used by man for the generation of power. Apart from these, geothermal energy is also an important energy source available in the form of geysers and hot springs. Solar, wind, hydrothermal, geothermal, biomass and biofuels are all called GREEN SOURCES OF ENERGY. Non-renewable sources of energy include nuclear energy and energy from coal and petroleum. Natural gas is also a good source of energy obtained from the decomposition of organic matter trapped between the layers of the earth. However, nuclear energy sources and also coal and petroleum are pollution-causing sources of energy. Whatever the energy sources, they need to be used judiciously, for a sustainable future.

Learning Objectives

- Understanding and appreciating the abundance of energy sources in the environment which make the Earth a liveable planet
- Gaining knowledge about how these energy sources can be harnessed for use
- Understanding the need to use these resources judiciously.